

Bending analysis of antisymmetric angle-ply laminates using HSDTs and the radial point interpolation method – Part I: Literature review and formulation

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Abstract

The mechanics of laminated plates is primarily studied using the Finite Element Method (FEM), which is often combined with plate models. Those plate models can be High-Order Shear Deformation Theories (HSDTs) since they accurately predict the nonlinear distributions of the shear stresses through-thickness. In this work, five HSDTs proposed in the literature are used to study the bending behavior of antisymmetric laminates with angle-ply layers. However, instead of using the traditional FEM, this study proposes the use of a meshless method: the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM). Meshless methods can offer some advantages over the FEM, such as in problems involving transitory geometries where the FEM may require re-meshing processes. In meshless methods, the shape functions have virtually a high order allowing higher continuity and reproducibility. Furthermore, they only require an unstructured nodal distribution discretizing the problem domain, meaning that there is no previous relationship between nodes, which simplifies the refinement procedure. In this first part of two articles, the RPIM and different HSDTs are combined to future analyze several antisymmetric angle-ply laminates in the second part. The RPIM's formulation is presented and the HSDT's are implemented within a meshless code.

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1. Introduction

Composite laminates are advanced materials composed of fibres mixed in a matrix in a layer-by-layer arrangement. Their main advantages over the most common metallic materials are their high specific mechanical properties which make them ideal to be used in advanced structures like aircraft, automobiles, vessels, wind blades, etc. Composite laminates offer high strength and low weight. Thus, the behaviour of such materials needs to be studied accurately in order to prevent failure mechanisms and to guarantee the integrity of the structure where they are being used.

One of the most common ways in which these materials appear in the engineering field is in a plate form. Plates are three-dimensional solids that can often be treated as a 2D simplification since their thickness is much smaller than their other dimensions. In those cases, the mechanical behaviour of the plate is studied through a plate theory. Plate theories interpolate the in-plane displacements of a plate through its thickness using different mathematical expressions. The first known plate theory is the one proposed by Gustav Kirchhoff. It was suggested in the middle of the 19th century and then it was developed by Augustus-Love in 1888 and, because of that, is now known as the Kirchhoff-Love plate theory or the Classical Plate Theory (CLPT). The assumptions of the Kirchhoff-Love are: (1) when a plate is subjected to a bending load, straight lines perpendicular to the mid-surface before deformation remain straight after deformation; (2) straight lines normal to the mid-surface remain normal to the mid-surface after deformation and (3) the plate does not experience elongation along with the thickness. Due to those considerations, the CLPT neglects shear effects that are predominantly found in thick and moderately thick laminated plates.

About 100 years later, Mindlin [1]–[4] developed the First-Order Shear Deformation Theory (FSDT), which considers shear effects. The assumptions of Mindlin are similar to the ones proposed by Kirchhoff but with a significant difference: straight lines perpendicular to the mid-surface before deformation remain straight but not necessarily normal to the mid-surface after deformation. Reissner, a few years after, developed a plate theory also including shear effects and they are both known nowadays as the Reissner-Mindlin plate theory. In the Reissner-Mindlin plate theory, the displacement field is obtained considering that the in-plane displacements are linearly distributed through the plate thickness. Thus, despite considering the shear effects, the FSDT predicts constant shear stresses across the thickness of the plate.

The interpolation of the in-plane displacements can be performed using higher-order functions (transverse shear functions) which also capture the non-linear behaviour observed in the distribution of the shear stresses across the laminate thickness. Such theories are called high-order shear deformation theories (HSDTs) and they can be used to predict with accuracy the mechanical behaviour of composite laminates. Additionally, HSDTs fulfil the traction boundary condition (zero shear stresses at the top and bottom faces of the plate) and do not need shear correction factors, unlike the FSDT. Each HSDT possesses a different transverse shear function which can have several mathematical forms such as polynomials [5]–[7], trigonometric [8], and hyperbolic [9], [10] functions, or the combination of trigonometric and exponential functions [11], etc.

The plate theories mentioned before are also called Equivalent Single Layer (ESL) Theories since they treat the laminate (composed of several layers) as a plate with just one layer. There are also layerwise (LW) theories (considering independent degrees of freedom for each layer) [12] and the zigzag (ZZ) theories [13] (where the kinematic behaviour is described on the whole laminate, and local refinement approach acts on the scale of the layer thickness [13]). These two approaches, even though being more accurate, are also computationally expensive. These plate models will not be analysed in this study.

The mechanical, vibrational, and dynamic analysis of composite laminates using HSDTs is not often performed through analytical procedures. Numerical tools like the Finite Element Method (FEM) or the Generalized Differential Quadrature (GDQ) method (which is a strong formulation of the governing equations applied in [14]–[17] to doubly-curved laminated composite shells and panels) offer easier ways to obtain solutions for complex problems. The FEM discretizes the problem domain in small sub-domains called elements. It is the association of these elements that forms a mesh where the nodal connectivity can be found. Since it is “mesh-reliant”, the FEM can find some limitations like the re-meshing process that is required in problems involving mesh distortion (large deformations, crack propagation, etc). Unlike the FEM, meshless methods only require an unstructured nodal distribution in order to discretize the problem domain. Thus, the concept of mesh or element does not exist [18]. The nodal connectivity is imposed by an overlapping rule of ‘influence-domains’ - areas or volumes in which the field variables are approximated. Meshless methods can offer some advantages when compared with the FEM. Meshless methods do not require re-meshing procedures, they have shape functions with a virtually higher order, allowing a higher continuity and reproducibility, and the refinement procedure is simpler – nodes can be added or removed from the nodal mesh [19].

This work makes use of a simple meshless method, the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) [20], to analyse the bending behaviour of antisymmetric angle-ply laminates using HDSTs. The RPIM uses radial interpolation functions, possessing the compact support and the delta Kronecker properties, to interpolate the field variables within ‘influence-domains’. To integrate the discrete system of equations obtained from the Galerkin weak form, a nodal independent background integration mesh is used, based on the Gauss-Legendre integration scheme. This makes the RPIM a ‘not truly meshless method’ since the mesh-free characteristic of the method is not verified [18]. In the following sections, the RPIM’s formulation is explained, the HSDTs are presented, and the framework of the developed in-house code is detailed.

2. Meshless Methods

It is useful to analyze meshless methods, as almost all kinds of numerical methods, through three fundamental parts: the field approximation (or interpolation) function, the used formulation and the integration [18]. Regarding the field approximation, meshless methods can be divided into approximant and interpolant meshless methods, depending on the type of shape functions used. Some of the most relevant approximant meshless methods use the Taylor approximation, the Moving Least-Square (MLS) approximation, the Reducing Kernel approximation, or the hp-cloud approximation. The Meshless Local Petrov-Galerkin Method (MLPG) [21], the Reproducing Kernel Particle Method (RKPM) [22] or the Finite Point Method (FPM) [23] are approximant meshless methods that appeared first but, despite their successful application to computational mechanics [19], they do not possess a very attractive and useful numerical property: the delta Kronecker property. Thus, interpolant meshless methods proposed more recently possess the delta Kronecker

property, simplifying the numerical imposition of the essential and natural boundary conditions. The Point Interpolation Method (PIM) [24] is a well know interpolant meshless method that has several versions, as can be found in the literature. The Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) [20] is a version of PIM since it makes use of its polynomial basis and it combines them with radial basis functions (RBF) to interpolate the field variables. The radial interpolation functions used in the RPIM possess the compact support and the delta Kronecker properties.

Meshless methods appeared first in 1977 when the Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics Method (SPH) [25] was proposed. Nevertheless, the considered first global weak form-based meshless method was only presented in 1994 with the development of the Element Free Galerkin Method (EFGM) [26], [27]. However, schemes based on the MSL initially gave birth to the actual first weak-form domain-type meshless method in 1992, named the Diffuse Element Method (DEM) [28] – which was then extended creating the EFGM.

Thus, in terms of formulation, the meshless methods can be classified, as the FEM, in two categories: strong and weak formulations. The RPIM uses the Galerkin weak form to obtain the discrete system of equations. In the literature, there are also meshless methods based on strong form formulations, but they are not analysed in this study.

Concerning the integration scheme, it can be performed using nodal dependent or nodal independent integration meshes. As already mentioned in the introductory section, the RPIM uses a nodal independent integration mesh that covers the problem domain, and it is composed of integration points (with correspondent integration weights). Other meshless methods, such as the one developed by Belinha et al. [29] – the Natural Neighbour Radial Point Interpolation Method (NNRPIM) - uses the Voronoï Diagram concept to determine ‘influence-cells’ and the integration scheme is based on that geometrical construction, creating an integration mesh dependent on the nodal mesh.

Other relevant meshless methods are the Point Assembly Method (PAM) [30], the Natural Element Method (NEM) [31], the Method of Finite Spheres (MFS) [32], or the Meshless Finite Element Method (MFEM) [33].

2.1. The RPIM formulation

In the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM), the nodes are arbitrarily distributed and they do not have any spatial relationship. Thus, in order to ensure the nodal connectivity, ‘influence-domains’ are constructed and overlapped.

The numerical procedure of the RPIM is initialized with the discretization of the problem domain in a set of nodes forming a regular or irregular nodal mesh (the irregular nodal mesh has, in general, lower accuracy). The next step is to create the integration mesh which, in the case of the RPIM, is based on the Gauss-Legendre integration scheme. The integration mesh can be fitted to the problem domain, or it can have a regular shape (in this case, it is necessary to remove the integration points placed outside the problem domain). The nodal independent background integration meshes constructed in the scope of this work are composed of quadrilateral cells (with isoparametric shape) containing integration points with a correspondent integration weight. Then, for each integration point of the integration mesh, the mentioned ‘influence-domains’ are defined. ‘Influence-domains’ are areas (for two-dimensional problems) or volumes (for three-dimensional problems), concentric with the integration points and containing a certain number of nodes of the nodal mesh. In this work, since the plate models are two-dimensional problems, ‘influence-domains’ are areas. These areas can contain a fixed number of nodes or a variable number of nodes, as suggested by Fig.1.

The literature recommends [18] the use of ‘influence-domains’ with a fixed number of nodes, between 9 and 16 nodes, which allows the construction of shape functions with the same degree of complexity. The different ‘influence-domains’ constructed for each integration point overlap each other, ensuring the nodal connectivity of the numerical method.

Using the ‘influence-domain’ concept, the field variables are interpolated. Thus, the displacement field at the interest point $\mathbf{x}_I$, $u(\mathbf{x}_I)$, is obtained interpolating the displacement fields observed in each node within the ‘influence-domain’ of $\mathbf{x}_I$, Eq. (1):

$$u(\mathbf{x}_I) = \sum_{j=1}^n \varphi_j(\mathbf{x}_I) \mathbf{u}_j \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of nodes within the ‘influence-domain’ of $\mathbf{x}_I$, $\mathbf{u}_j$ represents the displacements of each node j and $\varphi_j(\mathbf{x}_I)$ is the shape function of the node j obtained using the n nodes within the ‘influence-domain’ [29]. The

interpolation functions used in the RPIM are the result of the combination of multiquadric (MQ) radial basis functions (RBFs) and polynomial basis functions, and are presented in detail in the literature [29].

After the interpolation functions are calculated, the discrete system of equations is established from the Galerkin weak form (the meshless discrete system of equations is obtained in Appendix A), the boundary conditions are applied using, for instance, the Gauss elimination method [29], and solutions are found.

Fig.1 - (a) ‘Influence-domain’ with a fixed area ($r_I = r_J$); (b) ‘Influence-domain’ with a variable area ($r_I \neq r_J$) but a fixed number of nodes.

3. High-Order Shear Deformation Theories

Higher-Order Shear Deformation Theories (HSDTs) are Equivalent Single Layer Theories which allow higher accuracy than the First-Order Shear Deformation Theory (FSDT) when dealing with shear stresses. In the literature, it can be found several HSDTs that, as mentioned in the introductory section, have different transverse shear functions. The first proposed HSDT was the one developed by Ambartsumian [28], firstly applied to the analysis of anisotropic plates and shallow shells and later adapted for the analysis of composite materials. The Third-Order Shear Deformation Theory (TSDT) by J. N. Reddy [34] is probably the most well-known HSDT, although some works by Kant et al. [35]–[37], Levinson [38] and Murthy [39] about similar third-order theories are dated before Reddy’s. Shi [40], [41], [6] also developed a simple TSDT mathematically similar to Reddy’s theory. Nguyen-Xuan [42] also proposed a plate model using a fifth-degree polynomial as the transverse shear function (it is a Five-Order Shear Deformation Theory). Other authors proposed transverse shear functions that are not polynomials: Mantari [43], Karama [30] and Aydogdu [31] used exponential shape functions, Touratier [8] and Grover [46] consider trigonometric shape functions, Mantari [11] also developed shape functions which are combinations of exponential and trigonometric functions, Soldatos [47] and Meiche [10] made use of hyperbolic functions, etc.

This work uses five of these HSDTs in the bending analysis of antisymmetric angle-ply composite laminated plates. In this section, some of those HSDTs found in the literature are studied. Their displacement and strain fields are obtained and, in the end, the matrixes composing the discrete system of equations obtained in Appendix A are established.

3.1. Displacement Field. Strain-Stress Relations

Consider the plate represented in Fig.2, with dimensions a , b and h . Consider also that the plate is subjected to a generic load that produces displacements along with the directions of the coordinate axis $Oxyz$ – displacement $u(x, y, z)$ in direction Ox , $v(x, y, z)$ in direction Oy and $w(x, y, z)$ in direction Oz .

Fig. 2 – Generic geometry of a plate and coordinate system.

In Equivalent Single Layer (ESL) theories, those displacements can be written in terms of five independent degrees of freedom, three displacements along with the three coordinate axes, Ox , Oy and Oz , and two rotations: $u_0(x, y)$, $v_0(x, y)$, $w_0(x, y)$, $\phi_x(x, y)$ and $\phi_y(x, y)$,

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= u_0(x, y) + f(z) \cdot \left[\phi_x(x, y) + \frac{\partial w_0(x, y)}{\partial x} \right] - z \cdot \frac{\partial w_0(x, y)}{\partial x} \\ v(x, y, z) &= v_0(x, y) + f(z) \cdot \left[\phi_y(x, y) + \frac{\partial w_0(x, y)}{\partial y} \right] - z \cdot \frac{\partial w_0(x, y)}{\partial y} \\ w(x, y, z) &= w_0(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $f(z)$ is a transverse shear function depending on the variable z . Thus, if $f(z) = z$, Eq. (2) becomes the displacement field proposed by the FSDT:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= u_0(x, y) + z \cdot \phi_x(x, y) \\ v(x, y, z) &= v_0(x, y) + z \cdot \phi_y(x, y) \\ w(x, y, z) &= w_0(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Unlike the HSDTs, the FSDT does not verify the traction boundary conditions at the top and bottom faces of the plate since the shear stresses at those locations are not zero ($f'(h/2) = f'(-h/2) \neq 0$). The strain field is obtained by spatial derivation of the displacement field. Notice that for ESL theories, $\varepsilon_{zz} = 0$ - i.e. the component of the strain along with the Oz direction is considered null. The strain tensor can be written in the Voigt notation as: $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \{\varepsilon_{xx} \ \varepsilon_{yy} \ \gamma_{xy} \ \gamma_{yz} \ \gamma_{xz}\}^T$, whose components are determined in Eq. (4):

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + [f(z) - z] \cdot \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} + f(z) \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + [f(z) - z] \cdot \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} + f(z) \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} + 2[f(z) - z] \cdot \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} + f(z) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial x} \right) \\ f'(z) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} + \phi_y \right) \\ f'(z) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} + \phi_x \right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Thus, from Eq. (4) a differential operator, $\mathbf{L}$, can be established such that $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u}$, being $\mathbf{u} = [u_0 \ v_0 \ w_0 \ \phi_x \ \phi_y]^T$,

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & [f(z) - z] \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} & f(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & [f(z) - z] \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} & 0 & f(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 2[f(z) - z] \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} & f(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & f(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ 0 & 0 & f'(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & 0 & f'(z) \\ 0 & 0 & f'(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & f'(z) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{L}(z)$, since the differential operator depends on the transverse shear function, $f(z)$, and also on its derivative, $f'(z)$. The stress field is obtained from the strain field, using the Hooke's law: $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(k)} = \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, with $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(k)} = \{\sigma_{xx} \ \sigma_{yy} \ \tau_{xy} \ \tau_{yz} \ \tau_{xz}\}^T$ being the stress tensor, written in Voigt notation, for the layer k , and $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)}$ is the transformed reduced constitutive matrix for the same layer. $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)}$ depends on the angle formed between the local system of coordinates, $O123$, (in which direction 1 is the direction of the fibres) and the global system of coordinates, $Oxyz$, represented in Fig. 2 such that: $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} = \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{Q}^{(k)} \mathbf{T}$ (where $\mathbf{T}$ is the transformation matrix). The reduced elastic coefficients, $Q_{ij}^{(k)}$, are given by,

$$\mathbf{Q}^{(k)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_1^{(k)}}{(1 - \nu_{12}^{(k)} \nu_{21}^{(k)})} & \frac{(\nu_{12}^{(k)} E_2^{(k)})}{(1 - \nu_{12}^{(k)} \nu_{21}^{(k)})} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{(\nu_{12}^{(k)} E_2^{(k)})}{(1 - \nu_{12}^{(k)} \nu_{21}^{(k)})} & \frac{E_2^{(k)}}{(1 - \nu_{12}^{(k)} \nu_{21}^{(k)})} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12}^{(k)} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{23}^{(k)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{31}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where E_1 is the Young’s modulus of the composite laminate in the direction of the fibres, E_2 is the Young’s modulus of the in-plane transverse direction, ν_{ij} represents the Poisson’s ratio which measures the transverse deformation – direction j – related to an applied force in direction i and G_{ij} is the shear modulus characterizing the variation angle between directions i and j .

3.2. Transverse Shear Functions and Determination of the Deformation Matrixes

The transverse shear functions considered in this work are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 3.

Table 1 – Five high-order shear deformation theories whose formulation is used in this work.

HSDT	$f(z)$	$f'(z)$
Levinson [38], Murthy [39] and Reddy [5]	$z\left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{3h^2}\right)$	$1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2}$
Kaczkowski [40], Panc [41], Reissner [1] and Shi [6]	$\frac{5z}{4}\left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{3h^2}\right)$	$\frac{5}{4} - \frac{4z^2}{h^2}$
Ambartsumian [7]	$\frac{z}{2}\left(\frac{h^2}{4} - \frac{z^2}{3}\right)$	$\frac{h^2}{8} - \frac{z^2}{2}$
Touratier [8]	$\frac{h}{\pi}\sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right)$	$\cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right)$
Mantari [11]	$\frac{h}{\pi}\left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) \cdot e^{\frac{1}{2}\cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right)} + \frac{\pi z}{2h}\right]$	$\frac{1}{2} + e^{\frac{1}{2}\cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right)} \cdot \left[\cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \text{sen}^2\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right)\right]$

Fig. 3 – Distribution of the transverse shear functions, $f(z)$ for different HSDTs along with the normalized thickness z/h .

In order to obtain the displacement field suggested by each HSDTs, it is only necessary to replace the functions $f(z)$ in the expressions of Eq. (2). As can be seen in Table 1, the HSDTs considered in the scope of this work have different mathematical expressions defining the variation of the in-plane displacements across the plate thickness. The first three are Third-Order Shear Deformation Theories (TSDTs) already presented in the introduction of the present section. Reddy, Shi, and Ambartsumian are formally similar, and, because of that, they can be written in a standard form, which allows an easier computational implementation. Thus, the transverse shear functions can be written as: $f(z) = az + bz^3$, being a and b coefficients depending on the TSDT considered:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Reddy: } f(z) &= z \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{3h^2} \right) = z - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2}, \quad \{a, b\} = \left\{ 1, -\frac{4}{3h^2} \right\} \\ \text{Shi: } f(z) &= \frac{5}{4} z \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{3h^2} \right) = \frac{5}{4} z - \frac{5z^3}{3h^2}, \quad \{a, b\} = \left\{ \frac{5}{4}, -\frac{5}{3h^2} \right\} \\ \text{Ambartsumian: } f(z) &= \frac{z}{2} \left(\frac{h^2}{4} - \frac{z^2}{3} \right) = \frac{h^2}{8} z - \frac{z^3}{6}, \quad \{a, b\} = \left\{ \frac{h^2}{8}, -\frac{1}{6} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Analysing the coefficients a and b , it can be concluded that Reddy and Shi's theories are mathematically similar. Regarding Amabrtsumian's theory, and since the representation of its transverse shear function - see Fig. 3 - is almost equal to zero for the full range of z/h , it seems to have some similarities to the Classical Plate Theory (CLPT) which has no transverse shear function ($f(z)=0$).

The Touratier [8] model is also present in Table 1. It predicts the variation of the in-plane displacements along with the thickness of the plate as a trigonometric function, which can still be approximated in a unified polynomial form, as stated by Nguyen et al. [48]. The polynomial expansion of Touratier theory [44], [49] is given by:

$$\text{Touratier: } f(z) = \left(\frac{h}{\pi} \right) \sin \left(\frac{\pi z}{h} \right) = z - 1.645 \frac{z^3}{h^2} + 0.812 \frac{z^5}{h^4} - 0.191 \frac{z^7}{h^6} + 0.0261 \frac{z^9}{h^8} + \dots \quad (8)$$

When compared with Reddy's theory, it can be seen that the Touratier model has the same linear term coefficient and a similar coefficient for the cubic term of the polynomial. But, additionally to Reddy's theory, Touratier's plate model possesses terms with higher order than the third, which will lead to higher values for the shear stresses, as will be seen in a coming section.

The last theory presented in Table 1 is Mantari's HSDT [11], which has an exponential and a trigonometric part. The transverse shear function written in Table 1 can be generalized, being dependent on a parameter m - Eq. (9).

$$\text{Mantari: } f(z) = \frac{h}{\pi} \left(\sin \left(\frac{\pi z}{h} \right) e^{m \cos \left(\frac{\pi z}{h} \right)} + \frac{\pi z}{h} m \right), \quad m \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

Mantari optimized the parameter m and found that for $m = \frac{1}{2}$, the difference between his results and the solutions obtained from the 3D Elasticity approach were lowered. Thus, the transverse shear function presented in Table 1 uses $m = \frac{1}{2}$.

Substituting the transverse shear functions in Eq.(5), a different differential operator is obtained for each considered HSDT. As can be seen in detail in Appendix A, to obtain the stiffness matrix it is necessary to establish a deformation matrix, which is the product of the differential operator $L(z)$ by the matrix of interpolation functions, $H(x_i)$:

$B(x_i) = L(z) H(x_i)$. The matrix of the interpolation functions at the interest point x_i is given by:

$$\mathbf{H}_j(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} H_j(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & H_j(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & H_j(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & H_j(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & H_j(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{bmatrix}_j \quad j = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (10)$$

which is a $[5 \times 5n]$ matrix since there are five independent field variables, with n being the number of nodes within the ‘influence-domain’ of the interest point $\mathbf{x}_I$. Thus, established the differential operator, the deformation matrixes are easily obtained for the different HSDT considered: $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)|_{\text{TSDT}}$ (for Reddy, Shi and Amabrtsumian’s theories), $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)|_{\text{Touratier}}$ (for Touratier’s HSDT) and $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)|_{\text{Mantari}}$ (for Mantari’s HSDT).

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)|_{\text{TSDT}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & (az + bz^3 - z) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} & (az + bz^3) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & (az + bz^3 - z) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} & 0 & (az + bz^3) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 2(az + bz^3 - z) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} & (az + bz^3) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & (az + bz^3) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ 0 & 0 & (z + 3bz^2) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & 0 & (z + 3bz^2) \\ 0 & 0 & (z + 3bz^2) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & (z + 3bz^2) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)|_{\text{Touratier}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & \left[\frac{h}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) - z \right] \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} & \frac{h}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \left[\frac{h}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) - z \right] \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} & 0 & \frac{h}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 2 \left[\frac{h}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) - z \right] \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} & \frac{h}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{h}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ 0 & 0 & \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & 0 & \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) \\ 0 & 0 & \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)|_{\text{Mantari}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & \left[\frac{z}{2} + f_1(z) - z\right] \cdot \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} & \left[\frac{z}{2} + f_1(z)\right] \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \left[\frac{z}{2} + f_1(z) - z\right] \cdot \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} & 0 & \left[\frac{z}{2} + f_1(z)\right] \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 2 \cdot \left[\frac{z}{2} + f_1(z) - z\right] \cdot \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} & \left[\frac{z}{2} + f_1(z)\right] \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \left[\frac{z}{2} + f_1(z)\right] \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ 0 & 0 & \left[\frac{1}{2} + f_2(z)\right] \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & 0 & \left[\frac{1}{2} + f_2(z)\right] \\ 0 & 0 & \left[\frac{1}{2} + f_2(z)\right] \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \left[\frac{1}{2} + f_2(z)\right] & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \quad (13)$$

$$\text{where } f_1(z) = \frac{h}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) e^{\frac{1}{2} \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right)} \text{ and } f_2(z) = e^{\frac{1}{2} \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right)} \cdot \left(\cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right) - \frac{\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi z}{h}\right)}{2} \right).$$

3.3. Determination of the Stiffness Matrix

Using the integration scheme presented in subsection 2.2, the stiffness matrix can be obtained for a generic laminate,

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{c} \mathbf{B} \, d\Omega = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \, dz \right) \quad (14)$$

being nG the number of integration points used to integrate the stiffness matrix, $\hat{\omega}_I$ the integration weight of point $\mathbf{x}_I$, n_k the total number of layers of the laminate, $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)}$ the transformed reduced constitutive matrix of the layer k obtained for the coordinate system $Oxyz$ of Fig. 2, and finally, z_{k-1} and z_k the coordinates z of the bottom and top faces of the layer k .

Nevertheless, the integral (14) can be rewritten for an easier computational implementation. Thus, the deformation matrixes of Eq. (11)-(13) were divided into sub-matrixes, distinct from each other, and affected by distinct functions. For the TSDTs considered in this work, this process is exemplified below,

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)|_{\text{TSDT}} = \mathbf{B}_0 + az \cdot \mathbf{B}_1(\mathbf{x}_I) + 3bz^2 \cdot \mathbf{B}_2(\mathbf{x}_I) + bz^3 \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) + (az - z) \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) \quad (15)$$

where sub-.matrixes $\mathbf{B}_0$, $\mathbf{B}_1$, $\mathbf{B}_2$, $\mathbf{B}_3$ and $\mathbf{B}_4$ are given by,

$$\mathbf{B}_0^i(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y} & 0 & a \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ 0 & 0 & a \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x} & a \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 \end{bmatrix}_i \quad i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_1^i(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}_i \quad i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_2^i(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y} & 0 & \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x} & \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 \end{bmatrix}_i \quad i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_3^i(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x^2} & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y^2} & 0 & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y} \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x \partial y} & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}_i \quad i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_4^i(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x^2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial y^2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)}{\partial x \partial y} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}_i \quad i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (20)$$

Thus, the deformation sub-matrixes do not depend on the variable Z , so they are put outside of the integral in Eq. (14). Therefore, the stiffness matrix can be written as follows,

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{j=0}^4 \mathbf{K}_{ij} \quad (21)$$

which represents a sum of 25 matrixes $\mathbf{K}_{ij}$, with $i, j = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$. The matrixes $\mathbf{K}_{ij}$ are given as in equation (22). This homogenization procedure consists in separately summing the integrals of the constitutive matrixes affected by the terms of Eq. (15) that depend on the variable Z , through the thickness of each layer. Thus, the matrixes $\mathbf{c}_1$ to $\mathbf{c}_{15}$ are homogenized constitutive matrixes and obtained as in equation (23). This process allows reducing the computational cost of the algorithm. For the remaining HSDTs, a similar method was also adopted, although it is not detailed in this work.

4. Final Remarks

In the first part of the research work here presented, an extensive literature review on meshless methods and plates theory was performed. It was found that HSDTs are accurate approaches to predict the displacements in composite laminates since the traction boundary condition is satisfied and they do not need shear correction factors, unlike the FSDT. Five distinct HSDTs were selected to simulate, in the second part of this work, the mechanical performance of antisymmetric angle-ply laminated plates.

In order to do so, the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) will be used as main numerical technique – the RPIM's formulation was here shown with detail. Since it uses a background nodal independent integration mesh, where the Gauss-Legendre quadrature is implemented, RPIM is not a truly meshless method. However, this classification is not a disadvantage. In fact, since the RPIM shares the same integration scheme with FEM and both methods are interpolator discrete numerical methods, RPIM and FEM can be straightforwardly combined in the same analysis. Such combination would allow to use FEM the majority of the analyzed volume and use the RPIM only in the location in which it is necessary to update the nodal distribution (such as crack opening locations or locations with stress concentrations). Since the nodal connectivity is enforced by an overlapping rule of 'influence-domains', the RPIM does not depend on re-meshing processes in problems involving large deformation or fracture mechanics, unlike the FEM.

In the next part of this work, the formulation and computer implementation explained in the last sections will be used to compute displacements and stresses in several antisymmetric angle-ply laminates subjected to bending loads.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{K}_{00} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot \mathbf{B}_0(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_1 \cdot \mathbf{B}_0(\mathbf{x}_I) \\
\mathbf{K}_{01} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot k_1 \cdot z \cdot \mathbf{B}_1(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_2 \cdot \mathbf{B}_0(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{10} \\
\mathbf{K}_{02} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot 3k_2 z^2 \cdot \mathbf{B}_2(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_3 \cdot \mathbf{B}_0(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{20} \\
\mathbf{K}_{03} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot k_2 z^3 \cdot \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_4 \cdot \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{30} \\
\mathbf{K}_{04} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot (k_1 z - z) \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_0^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_5 \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{40} \\
\mathbf{K}_{11} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_1^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot (k_1 z)^2 \cdot \mathbf{B}_1(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_1^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_6 \cdot \mathbf{B}_1(\mathbf{x}_I) \\
\mathbf{K}_{12} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_1^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot (k_1 z) \cdot (3k_2 z^2) \cdot \mathbf{B}_2(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_1^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_7 \cdot \mathbf{B}_2(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{21} \\
\mathbf{K}_{13} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_1^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot (k_1 z) \cdot (k_2 z^3) \cdot \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_1^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_8 \cdot \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{31} \\
\mathbf{K}_{14} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_1^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot k_1 z \cdot (k_1 z - z) \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_1^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_9 \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{41} \\
\mathbf{K}_{22} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_2^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot (3k_2 z^2)^2 \cdot \mathbf{B}_2(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_2^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_{10} \cdot \mathbf{B}_2(\mathbf{x}_I) \\
\mathbf{K}_{23} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_2^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot (3k_2 z^2 \cdot k_2 z^3) \cdot \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_2^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_{11} \cdot \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{32} \\
\mathbf{K}_{24} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_2^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot [3k_2 z^2 \cdot (k_1 z - z)] \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_2^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_{12} \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{42} \\
\mathbf{K}_{33} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_3^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot (k_2 z^3)^2 \cdot \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_3^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_{12} \cdot \mathbf{B}_3(\mathbf{x}_I) \\
\mathbf{K}_{34} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_3^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot [k_2 z^3 \cdot (k_1 z - z)] \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_3^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_{14} \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{K}_{43} \\
\mathbf{K}_{44} &= \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \mathbf{B}_4^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{Q}}^{(k)} \cdot [(k_1 z - z) \cdot (k_1 z - z)] \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I) dz = \sum_{I=1}^{nG} \hat{\omega}_I \cdot \mathbf{B}_4^T(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{c}_{15} \cdot \mathbf{B}_4(\mathbf{x}_I)
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
c_1 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} dz = \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} (z_k - z_{k-1}) \cdot \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_2 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot a z dz = k_1 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^2}{2} - \frac{z_{k-1}^2}{2} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_3 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot 3b z^2 dz = 3b \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^3}{3} - \frac{z_{k-1}^3}{3} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_4 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot b z^3 dz = b \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^4}{4} - \frac{z_{k-1}^4}{4} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_5 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot (a z - z) dz = (a-1) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^2}{2} - \frac{z_{k-1}^2}{2} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_6 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot (a z)^2 dz = a^2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^3}{3} - \frac{z_{k-1}^3}{3} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_7 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot (a z) \cdot (3b z^2) dz = 3ab \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^4}{4} - \frac{z_{k-1}^4}{4} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_8 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot (a z) \cdot (b z^3) dz = a \cdot b \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^5}{5} - \frac{z_{k-1}^5}{5} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_9 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot a z \cdot (a z - z) dz = a \cdot (a-1) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^3}{3} - \frac{z_{k-1}^3}{3} \right) \bar{Q}_k^{(k)} \\
c_{10} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot (3b z^2)^2 dz = 9b^2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^5}{5} - \frac{z_{k-1}^5}{5} \right) \bar{Q}_k^{(k)} \\
c_{11} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot (3b z^2 \cdot b z^3) dz = 3b^2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^6}{6} - \frac{z_{k-1}^6}{6} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_{12} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot 3b z^2 \cdot (a z - z) dz = 3b(a-1) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^6}{6} - \frac{z_{k-1}^6}{6} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_{13} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot (b z^3)^2 dz = b^2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^7}{7} - \frac{z_{k-1}^7}{7} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_{14} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot b z^3 \cdot (a z - z) dz = b \cdot (a-1) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^5}{5} - \frac{z_{k-1}^5}{5} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)} \\
c_{15} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \bar{Q}^{(k)} \cdot (a z - z) \cdot (a z - z) dz = (a-1) \cdot (a-1) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} \left(\frac{z_k^3}{3} - \frac{z_{k-1}^3}{3} \right) \bar{Q}^{(k)}
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

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References

- [1] E. Reissner, "On the theory of transverse bending of elastic plates," *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 545–554, 1976.
- [2] E. Reissner, "A consistent treatment of transverse shear deformations in laminated anisotropic plates," *AIAA J.*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 716–718, 1972, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2514/3.50194>.
- [3] E. Reissner, "The effect of transverse shear deformations on the bending of elastic plates," *J. Appl. Mech.*, vol. 12, pp. A69–A77, 1945.
- [4] R. D. Mindlin, "Influence of Rotatory Inertia and Shear on Flexural Motions of Isotropic, Elastic Plates," *J. Appl. Mech.*, no. 18, pp. 31–38, 1951.
- [5] J.N. Reddy, "Mechanics of laminated composite plates and shells: theory and analysis." CRC Press LLC, Boca Raton, Florida, 2004, doi: 10.1007/978-1-4471-0095-9.
- [6] G. Shi, "A new simple third-order shear deformation theory of plates," *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 44, no. 13, pp. 4399–4417, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2006.11.031.
- [7] S. A. Ambartsumian, "On the theory of bending of anisotropic plates and shallow shells," *J. Appl. Math. Mech.*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 500–514, Jan. 1960, doi: 10.1016/0021-8928(60)90052-6.
- [8] M. Touratier, "An efficient standard plate theory," *Int. J. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 29, no. 8, pp. 901–916, 1991.
- [9] K. P. Soldatos, "A transverse shear deformation theory for homogeneous monoclinic plates," *Acta Mech.*, vol. 94, no. 3–4, pp. 195–220, 1992.
- [10] N. El, A. Tounsi, N. Ziane, I. Mechab, E. Abbes, and A. Bedia, "A new hyperbolic shear deformation theory for buckling and vibration of functionally graded sandwich plate," *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 237–247, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.ijmesci.2011.01.004.
- [11] J. L. Mantari, A. S. Oktem, and C. Guedes Soares, "A new higher order shear deformation theory for sandwich and composite laminated plates," *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 1489–1499, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2011.07.017.
- [12] a J. M. Ferreira, "Analysis of Composite Plates Using a Layerwise Theory and Multiquadrics Discretization," *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 99–112, 2005, [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15376490490493952>.
- [13] L. Iurlaro, M. Gherlone, M. Di Sciuva, and A. Tessler, "Refined Zigzag Theory for laminated composite and sandwich plates derived from Reissner's Mixed Variational Theorem," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 133, pp. 809–817, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.08.004.
- [14] E. Viola, F. Tornabene, and N. Fantuzzi, "General higher-order shear deformation theories for the free vibration analysis of completely doubly-curved laminated shells and panels," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 95, pp. 639–666, 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.08.005>.
- [15] E. Viola, F. Tornabene, and N. Fantuzzi, "Static analysis of completely doubly-curved laminated shells and panels using general higher-order shear deformation theories," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 101, pp. 59–93, 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.01.002>.
- [16] F. Tornabene, E. Viola, and N. Fantuzzi, "General higher-order equivalent single layer theory for free vibrations of doubly-curved laminated composite shells and panels," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 104, pp. 94–117, 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.04.009>.
- [17] F. Tornabene, N. Fantuzzi, and M. Baccocchi, "The local GDQ method applied to general higher-order theories of doubly-curved laminated composite shells and panels: The free vibration analysis," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 116, pp. 637–660, 2014, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.05.008>.
- [18] J. Belinha, *Meshless Methods in Biomechanics: Bone Tissue Remodelling Analysis*. Porto: Springer International Publishing, 2014.
- [19] J. Belinha, A. L. Araújo, A. J. M. Ferreira, L. M. J. S. Dinis, and R. M. N. Jorge, "The analysis of laminated plates using distinct advanced discretization meshless techniques," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 143, pp. 165–179, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2016.02.021.
- [20] J. G. Wang and G. R. Liu, "A point interpolation meshless method based on radial basis functions," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 54, no. 11, pp. 1623–1648, 2002.
- [21] S. N. Atluri and T. Zhu, "A new Meshless Local Petrov-Galerkin (MLPG) approach in computational mechanics," *Comput. Mech.*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 117–127, 1998.
- [22] W. K. Liu, S. Jun, S. Li, J. Adee, and T. Belytschko, "Reproducing kernel particle methods for structural dynamics," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 38, no. 10, pp. 1655–1679, 1995, doi: 10.1002/nme.1620381005.
- [23] E. Oñate, S. Idelsohn, O. C. Zienkiewicz, and R. L. Taylor, "A finite point method in computational mechanics. Applications to convective transport and fluid flow," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 39, no. December 1995, pp. 3839–3866, 1996.
- [24] G. R. Liu and Y. T. Gu, "A point interpolation method for two-dimensional solids," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 937–951, 2001.
- [25] R. A. Gingold and J. J. Monaghan, "Smoothed particle hydrodynamics: theory and application to non-spherical stars," *Mon. Not. R. Astron. Soc.*, vol. 181, no. 3, pp. 375–389, 1977, doi: 10.1093/mnras/181.3.375.
- [26] T. Belytschko, Y. Y. Lu, and L. Gu, "Element-free Galerkin methods," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in*

- Engineering*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 229–256, 1994, doi: 10.1002/nme.1620370205.
- [27] J. N. R. M. Noronha, J.; Belinha, J., Dinis, L., “The Numerical Analysis of Airplane Windshields due to Bird Strike: A Static Study,” *Fac. Eng. Univ. Porto*, 2016.
- [28] B. Nayroles, G. Touzot, and P. Villon, “Generalizing the finite element method: Diffuse approximation and diffuse elements,” *Comput. Mech.*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 307–318, 1992, doi: 10.1007/BF00364252.
- [29] J. Belinha, L. M. J. S. Dinis, and R. M. N. Jorge, “The Natural Neighbour Radial Point Interpolation Method: Solid Mechanics and Mechanobiology Applications,” *Fac. Eng. da Univ. do Porto*, 2010.
- [30] G. R. Liu, “A point assembly method for stress analysis for two-dimensional solids,” *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 261–276, 2001.
- [31] N. Sukumar, B. Moran, and T. Belytschko, “The natural element method in solid mechanics,” *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 839–887, 1998, doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1097-0207(19981115)43:5<839::AID-NME423>3.0.CO;2-R.
- [32] S. De and K. J. Bathe, “The method of finite spheres,” *Comput. Mech.*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 329–345, 2000, doi: 10.1007/s004660050481.
- [33] I. S. R., O. Eugenio, C. Nestor, and D. P. Facundo, “The meshless finite element method,” *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 893–912, Jul. 2003, doi: 10.1002/nme.798.
- [34] J. N. Reddy, “A refined nonlinear theory of plates with transverse shear deformation,” *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 20, no. 9–10, pp. 881–896, 1984.
- [35] T. Kant, “Numerical analysis of thick plates,” *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 1–18, 1982, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7825\(82\)90043-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7825(82)90043-3).
- [36] T. Kant, D. R. J. Owen, and O. C. Zienkiewicz, “A refined higher-order C^0 plate bending element,” *Comput. Struct.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 177–183, 1982, doi: 10.1016/0045-7949(82)90065-7.
- [37] B. N. Pandya and T. Kant, “A refined higher-order generally orthotropic $C0$ plate bending element,” *Comput. Struct.*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 119–133, 1988, doi: 10.1016/0045-7949(88)90031-4.
- [38] M. Levinson, “An accurate simple theory of the statics and dynamics of elastic plates,” *Mech. Res. Commun*, no. 7, pp. 343–350, 1980.
- [39] M. V. V. Murthy, “An improved transverse shear deformation theory for laminated anisotropic plates,” *NASA Tech. Pap.* 1903, no. November, 1981.
- [40] Z. Kaczkowski, *Plates. In Statical calculations*. Warszawa (in Polish): Arkady, 1968.
- [41] V. Panc, *Theories of elastic plates*, 1st ed. Prague: Academia, 1975.
- [42] H. Nguyen-Xuan, C. H. Thai, and T. Nguyen-Thoi, “Isogeometric finite element analysis of composite sandwich plates using a higher order shear deformation theory,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 55, pp. 558–574, 2013.
- [43] J. L. Mantari, A. S. Oktem, and C. G. Soares, “Static and dynamic analysis of laminated composite and sandwich plates and shells by using a new higher-order shear deformation theory,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 94, no. 1, pp. 37–49, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2011.07.020.
- [44] M. Karama, K. S. Afaq, and S. Mistou, “A new theory for laminated composite plates,” *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part L J. Mater. Des. Appl.*, vol. 223, no. 2, pp. 53–62, 2009, doi: 10.1243/14644207JMDA189.
- [45] M. Aydogdu, “A new shear deformation theory for laminated composite plates,” *Compos. Struct. J.*, no. 89, pp. 94–101, 2008.
- [46] N. Grover, B. N. Singh, and D. K. Maiti, “New Nonpolynomial Shear-Deformation Theories for Structural Behavior of Laminated-Composite and Sandwich Plates,” *AIAA J.*, vol. 51, no. 8, pp. 1861–1871, 2013, [Online]. Available: <http://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/1.J052399>.
- [47] K. P. Soldatos, “A transverse shear deformation theory for homogeneous monoclinic plates,” *Acta Mech.*, 1992, doi: 10.1007/BF01176650.
- [48] T. N. Nguyen, C. H. Thai, and H. Nguyen-Xuan, “On the general framework of high order shear deformation theories for laminated composite plate structures: A novel unified approach,” *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, vol. 110, pp. 242–255, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2016.01.012.
- [49] A. Idlbi, M. Karama, and M. Touratier, “Comparison of various laminated plate theories,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 173–184, 1997, [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263822397800104>.
- [50] L. M. J. S. Dinis, R. M. Natal Jorge, and J. Belinha, “Analysis of plates and laminates using the natural neighbour radial point interpolation method,” *Eng. Anal. Bound. Elem.*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 267–279, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.enganbound.2007.08.006.

Appendix A - Meshless discrete system of equations

The RPIM uses the Galerkin weak form formulation to obtain the discrete system of equations ruling the problem. The Galerkin weak is determined minimizing the Lagrangian functional written for a generic solid with domain Ω and boundary Γ , that contain all physical information about the problem and the forces acting on it:

$$\delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left[\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{\mathbf{u}}^T \dot{\mathbf{u}} d\Omega - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{u}^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma \right] dt = 0 \quad (24)$$

being $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ the velocity, ρ the solid mass density, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ the strain tensor, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ the stress tensor, $\mathbf{u}$ the displacements vector, $\mathbf{b}$ the body forces, $\Gamma \in \Omega$ the traction boundary where the external forces $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ are applied and t_1 and t_2 any initial and final time, respectively. The work here described only concerns static analysis, thus, the first term of the integrand in Eq. (24) is discarded:

$$\delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left[-\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{u}^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma \right] dt = 0 \quad (25)$$

Moving the variation operator δ inside the integrals,

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left[-\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \delta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}) d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma \right] dt = 0 \quad (26)$$

Considering that, for the Eq. (26) be satisfied for all possible $\mathbf{u}$ and for any initial and final time, t_1 and t_2 , the integrand must be null, the ‘Galerkin weak form’ is established,

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma \quad (27)$$

being $\delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ the virtual strain tensor and $\delta \mathbf{u}$ the virtual displacement. The discrete system of equations is established from Eq. (27) by introducing the stress-strain relation, $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{c} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ (being $\mathbf{c}$ is the constitutive matrix), the linear relation between strains and displacements: $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{L} \mathbf{u}$ (being $\mathbf{L}$ the differential operator established in **Erro! A origem da referência não foi encontrada.** and $\mathbf{u} = \{u_0 \ v_0 \ w_0 \ \phi_x \ \phi_y\}^T$) and also the equations of interpolation: $u(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{j=1}^n \varphi_j(\mathbf{x}_1) \mathbf{u}_j$ and $\delta u(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{j=1}^n \varphi_j(\mathbf{x}_1) \delta \mathbf{u}_j$. From those considerations, the concept of deformation matrix is found: $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{L} \varphi_j(\mathbf{x}_1)$, such as $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_1) = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_1) \mathbf{u}_1$, being $\mathbf{u}_1$ the vector contain the nodal values. Thus, the discrete system of equations is obtained,

$$\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{c} \mathbf{B} d\Omega \cdot \mathbf{u} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H} \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma \quad (28)$$

where matrix $\mathbf{H}$ is the same that was introduced in subsection 3.2. Eq. (28) can be written in a standard form:

$$\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{F} \quad (29)$$

with $\mathbf{K} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{c} \mathbf{B} \, d\Omega$ and $\mathbf{F} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{b} \, d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H} \bar{\mathbf{t}} \, d\Gamma$. For the problem in analysis in this work, the force vector in (29) is given by the sum of the vector of the body forces, $\mathbf{f}_b = \int_A \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}) \{f_x \ f_y \ f_z \ 0 \ 0\}^T \, dA$, with f_x , f_y and f_z being the body forces along x , y and z directions, respectively, and A being the area of the plate, and the vector of the external surface forces, $\mathbf{f}_e = \int_A \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}) \{0 \ 0 \ p_z \ 0 \ 0\}^T \, dA$, where p_z is an external solicitation on the plate along with the axis Oz , producing a bending behaviour. The stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}$ is established in subsection 3.3. The meshless discrete system of equations here briefly established is detailed shown in the literature [18], [19], [50].